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Systematic discovery of therapeutic targets in lymph node metastasis.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We integrated transcriptomic identification of gene products based on differential expression in metastatic versus primary tumor tissue with study of human survival in a large cohort of humans with breast cancer for over 20 years (250 months) for drug discovery using a novel systems biologic approach. Analysis of time to death following metastasis to a distant site (distant metastasis-free survival) for all up-regulated targets in the top 0.5% of the lymph node metastasis transcriptome indicated broad functionality in the cancer transcriptome with strong therapeutic potential for approximately one quarter (25%) of all identified targets.